

VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY IN POSTMENOPAUSAL WOMEN

¹Amonova Madina Furkatovna, ²Ochilova Nusratoy Ismoil qizi, ³Shernazarov Farrukh

¹Samarkand State Medical University

Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology No. 1

^{2,3}Samarkand State Medical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10335546>

Abstract. *These words evoke a storm of conflicting emotions in every woman. On the one hand, we understand that this is an inevitable but natural process. On the other hand, during this period of life, chronic diseases can become active in women, and mental depression, nervous disorders, insomnia, hot flashes, feeling of heat, excessive sweating, can appear suddenly, which is called menopause syndrome. mood swings, obesity, etc.*

Keywords: *menopause, premenopause, perimenopause and postmenopause.*

SYMPTOMS OF MENOPAUSE

According to statistics, menopause syndrome occurs in four out of five women. At the same time, severe and moderate course occurs in the majority of patients, and only 16% of women have a mild course. Realizing that menopausal women are on the threshold of new opportunities (children are already grown, grandchildren are grown, professional and social life is well established), it is at this time that they have the opportunity to pay more attention to themselves. First, let's look at the classification of menopause periods. To know this, it is necessary to know that everything starts long before the onset of menopause, sometimes even 10-15 years, and continues almost for our entire future life.

Therefore, we distinguish the following stages:

premenopause - the period of transition to menopause;

menopause;

perimenopause and postmenopause.

Premenopause begins at the age of 40-45 and ends with the onset of menopause. Menstrual cycles may be irregular during this period.

Menopause is the last independent menstruation in a woman's life. Menopause can be natural or artificial. The average age of natural menopause for women in Ukraine is 52.5 years. During menopause, in women, against the background of the decrease in the hormonal function of the ovaries, there is a general decrease in the level of all female sex hormones, but the rate of their decrease is different, that is, the level of progesterone decreases twice as fast. estrogen levels. Therefore, during this period, women experience the so-called relative increase in estrogen levels, which can lead to the development of hyperplastic (or oncological) processes of any localization.

There is also a classification according to the age of onset of menopause:

Early ovarian failure before the age of 40;

early menopause at the age of 40-45;

Timely menopause at the age of 46-54;

Late menopause after 55 years.

According to statistics, only one percent of women experience early menopause, and only one percent of women continue to menstruate until the age of 60. The onset of menopause is accelerated: removal of the uterus, smoking, stress, surgical interventions on the organs of the

reproductive system, lack of fertility, low level of education, living at an altitude of more than two thousand meters above sea level, loneliness and other negative factors.

MENOPAUSE SYNDROME

Let's see what climacteric syndrome is. These are various pathological conditions that occur in women against the background of a decrease in the hormonal function of the ovaries and the general age-related involution of the body; they are caused by genetic factors, previous somatic diseases, parity, environmental conditions and social factors. Therefore, let's look at the main symptoms (disorders, symptoms) of menopause syndrome, which differ in the time of onset and can be early, long and late. They are also distinguished by types of systemic diseases. Therefore, the initial symptoms include: vasomotor and psycho-emotional.

The most popular vasomotor symptoms:

hot flashes;

increased sweating;

Headache; lability of blood pressure;

trembling;

tachycardia;

extrasystoles;

dizziness.

A group of psycho-emotional symptoms:

increased fatigue;

nervousness;

mood swings;

sleep disorder;

weakness;

anxiety;

depression;

neglect;

decreased libido.

The group of long-term symptoms includes urogenital diseases, changes in the skin and its appendages. During this period, women often suffer from: atrophic vaginitis, vaginal dryness, itching and burning in the external genitalia or vagina, pain during intercourse, urinary incontinence, dysuria, cystitis. In the initial stages, these diseases are completely cured. Of course, we women do not like dry and brittle nails and hair, dry skin and hair loss. Here it is necessary to consider which vitamins should be chosen for a woman during menopause. In addition, it should be taken into account that the exacerbation of menopause syndrome occurs in the winter-spring and autumn periods. The diagnosis of perimenopause and menopause does not require additional laboratory hormonal tests for most healthy women after the age of forty-five if the following symptoms are present: Vasomotor symptoms due to irregular menstruation during perimenopause and the absence of menstruation in the last twelve months (without the use of hormonal contraceptives) or the appearance of menopausal symptoms after hysterectomy - in postmenopause.

Note that there are many reasons for the appearance of pathological conditions similar to menopause syndrome. Therefore, doctors make a differential diagnosis, taking into account the age of the patient. In young women, first of all, pregnancy should be excluded.

NUTRITION DURING MENOPAUSE

Many women are afraid of the onset of menopause, worried about changes in appearance, weight gain and hot flashes. In fact, everything turns out to be much easier, and in cases where symptoms appear, it is corrected with medication. Accept menopause as a natural physiological process and transition to a new phase of life. Eat a balanced diet to get all the vitamins your body needs during menopause, including vitamin D and minerals. It reduces the risk of osteoporosis and weight gain during menopause. Maintain a healthy weight with a balanced, low-sugar diet. Fill your food with vitamins and minerals. Exercise regularly. Even moderate exercise, such as walking for half an hour 3 times a week, is beneficial. If you are considering hormone replacement therapy, discuss the risks and benefits with your doctor first. Smoking is a major risk factor for heart disease. Control high blood pressure with medication or lifestyle changes. It helps reduce the risk of heart disease. Reduce stress in your life through relaxation techniques or regular exercise. We recommend discussing all changes in the body during this period with a gynecologist. Learning reliable information can help reduce stress and prevent mood swings, depression, and sleep problems.

THE ROLE OF VITAMINS IN WOMEN'S BODY

It's no secret that healthy lifestyle habits, including adequate exercise and nutrition, and menopause vitamins are important at all stages of life. This includes making sure you're getting enough vitamins and minerals, especially those that may require more conscious effort to get. Vitamin D is one of the nutrients we hear about the most, and it's especially important in middle age.

Vitamin D performs many functions in the body:

- stimulates the absorption of calcium;
- supports bone health;
- it supports the immune system;
- reduces inflammation;
- helps improve mood and sleep;

It helps to overcome depression, which is especially noticeable at this age. A question often arises: what are the best vitamins for menopause or those over 50? Getting enough vitamin D to support these functions is certainly necessary throughout life, but may be especially important during menopause. Because of the natural, progressive loss of skeletal integrity after menopause, additional skeletal deterioration associated with vitamin D deficiency should be avoided. Furthermore, epidemiologic studies suggest that increased vitamin D intake and the risk of vitamin D deficiency is lower. from early menopause. Vitamin D has been studied for its potential association with some menopausal symptoms. Because calcium absorption and storage (which requires adequate vitamin D) decreases after menopause, it has been hypothesized that vitamin D levels may influence other hormone-related symptoms during this stage of life. However, vitamin D is still needed in middle age for many other reasons.

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF ELIMINATING MENOPAUSE SYMPTOMS

Lifestyle changes can also be an effective step in managing menopause symptoms. Because menopause can affect women differently, treatment should be sought based on symptoms.

Hot Flashes: If you have hot flashes, keep your room cool and dress in layers to regulate your body temperature by removing or wearing extra clothing. Avoid alcohol and spicy foods as they can aggravate hot flash symptoms.

Weight and Cholesterol Gain: During menopause, women are more likely to gain weight, especially in the middle section. Menopausal changes can also make it harder to control cholesterol levels. Counteract this by eating a clean diet that includes fruits, vegetables, and organic, low-fat proteins like chicken or fish. Drink plenty of water and avoid processed foods.

Bone loss: Decreased levels of the hormone estrogen can accelerate bone loss. Weight-bearing exercises such as walking, jogging, and strength training help maintain bone strength.

COMPLEX OF VITAMINS AND MINERALS FOR MENOPAUSE

Hormonal changes during menopause cause many side effects, including an increased risk of certain diseases and conditions. As estrogen declines, the risk of osteoporosis and heart disease increases, as does the tendency to suffer from symptoms such as hot flashes, mood swings, and vaginal dryness. To combat this, menopause vitamins and supplements can be a key component of a woman's care during and after menopause, but the process of deciding which ones to take can be overwhelming. When it comes to menopause supplements, there is no single pill.

WHAT ARE THE BEST VITAMINS FOR MENOPAUSE, HOW TO CHOOSE THE RIGHT VITAMINS FOR THE OVER 50S

When choosing a complex or a single drug, consider the presence of necessary vitamins in the composition and the appropriate dose depending on your age. For example, daily maintenance doses of 2,000 to 4,800 IU per day are recommended to correct vitamin D deficiency. Taking vitamin D supplements is a modern, safe and reliable alternative to traditional ways of getting this vitamin into our bodies. It also reduces hair loss due to vitamin D deficiency. During this period of life, vitamin D has a positive effect on a woman's nervous system, helps reduce stress and improves emotional well-being. Scientists have proven that vitamin D receptors are located in the areas of the brain where serotonin and dopamine are produced, which are called "hormones of happiness" or "hormones of good mood". They are responsible for forming positive emotions and memories. People with low mood and depression usually have low levels of vitamin D in their bodies. A sufficient amount of vitamin D in the female body contributes to weight loss by normalizing metabolism and increasing the overall tone of the body.

REFERENCES

1. Furkatovna, A. M. (2022). EFFECT OF VITAMIN D DICTION ON BONE MINERAL DENSITY IN MENOPAUSA WOMEN. *World Bulletin of Public Health*, 7, 121-123.
2. Furkatovna, A. M. (2022). EFFECT OF VITAMIN D DICTION ON BONE MINERAL DENSITY IN MENOPAUSA WOMEN. *World Bulletin of Public Health*, 7, 121-123.
3. Furkatovna, A. M., & Dilmurod o'g, K. U. B. (2023). New Approaches to Rehabilitation After Ectopic Pregnancy. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 4(2), 282-285.
4. Tugizova, D., Amonova, M., & Farmonova, D. (2022). PROGNOSTIC FACTORS OF CERVICAL CANCER IN PREGNANT WOMEN. *Science and innovation*, 1(D7), 292-296.
5. Tugizova, D., Amonova, M., & Farmonova, D. (2022). PROGNOSTIC FACTORS OF CERVICAL CANCER IN PREGNANT WOMEN. *Science and Innovation*, 1(7), 292-296.
6. Amonova, M., & Tugizova, D. (2022). ВЛИЯНИЕ СОДЕРЖАНИЕ ВИТАМИНА Д НА ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ МИНЕРАЛЬНОЙ ПЛОТНОСТИ КОСТНОЙ ТКАНИ У ЖЕНЩИН В МЕНОПАУЗЕ. *Science and innovation*, 1(D7), 234-239.

7. Shernazarov Farrukh ORGANIZATION OF DIGITALIZED MEDICINE AND HEALTH ACADEMY AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN MEDICINE // SAI. 2023. №Special Issue 8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/organization-of-digitalized-medicine-and-health-academy-and-its-significance-in-medicine> (дата обращения: 20.11.2023).
8. Furkatovna, A. M., & Dilmurod o'g, K. U. B. (2023). New Approaches to Rehabilitation After Ectopic Pregnancy. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 4(2), 282-285.
9. Tugizova, D., Amonova, M., & Farmonova, D. (2022). PROGNOSTIC FACTORS OF CERVICAL CANCER IN PREGNANT WOMEN. Science and innovation, 1(D7), 292-296.
10. Tugizova, D., Amonova, M., & Farmonova, D. (2022). PROGNOSTIC FACTORS OF CERVICAL CANCER IN PREGNANT WOMEN. Science and Innovation, 1(7), 292-296.
11. Amonova, M., & Tugizova, D. (2022). ВЛИЯНИЕ СОДЕРЖАНИЕ ВИТАМИНА Д НА ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ МИНЕРАЛЬНОЙ ПЛОТНОСТИ КОСТНОЙ ТКАНИ У ЖЕНЩИН В МЕНОПАУЗЕ. Science and innovation, 1(D7), 234-239.
12. Shernazarov Farrukh ORGANIZATION OF DIGITALIZED MEDICINE AND HEALTH ACADEMY AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN MEDICINE // SAI. 2023. №Special Issue 8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/organization-of-digitalized-medicine-and-health-academy-and-its-significance-in-medicine> (дата обращения: 20.11.2023).